

MOLECULAR DESIGN OF HIGH PERFORMANCE POLYMERIC MATERIAL MATRIX RESINS AND STRUCTURAL ADHESIVES: POLY(ARYLENE ETHER)S AS TOUGHNESS MODIFIERS FOR CYANATE ESTER NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Cyanate ester networks are receiving considerable attention as potential candidates for high temperature adhesives and composite matrices. An inherent brittleness is a major drawback with most cross-linked thermosetting materials and the cyanate ester networks are no exception. Considerable attention has been devoted to the aspect of toughening such brittle networks in our laboratories. Over the years we have convincingly demonstrated how the use of reactive functional thermoplastic toughness modifiers help not only in enhancing toughness but also in imparting highly desirable stability to solvent stress cracking. We have investigated and reported on different aspects of this technology as has been applied to various systems. In the present work, we have sought to advance this general study by focusing on modifications of a specific cyanate ester network system based on Bisphenol-A with thermoplastic modifiers of varying back-bone molecular weight and chemistry.

Keywords: cyanate ester networks, reactive functional thermoplastic toughness modifiers

1. INTRODUCTION

Epoxy and bismaleimides are currently important thermosetting materials for high performance adhesives and advanced composite matrix applications both in the aerospace and electronic industries. These tightly cross-linked networks combine excellent thermal and mechanical properties with outstanding adhesive properties. However, their widespread use is limited in many high performance applications owing to an inherent brittle behavior.

Traditional toughness modifiers such as carboxy terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile copolymers (CTBN) have been widely reported (1,2), to help enhance toughness but this is achieved at the expense of high temperature performance. This has been attributed to the low glass transition temperature of the rubbery phase which lowers the use temperature and the modulus of the resulting networks. Toughening studies employing commercial (non-reactive) thermoplastic modifiers have not always proven successful possibly due to poor adhesion between the substrate and the modifier as well as unacceptable loss of chemical resistance due to the amorphous non-reactive thermoplastic. In our laboratory (3,4) and elsewhere (5), it has been demonstrated that the above mentioned limitations can be effectively overcome by the incorporation of tough, ductile, functionally terminated, high temperature thermoplastic modifiers. The failure of thermosetting high cross-link density networks is known to primarily occur by localized shear yielding and plastic deformation mechanisms. The incorporation of thermoplastic modifiers is believed to cause desirable bulk shear yielding and plastic deformation and thereby enhance toughness. Improvements in toughness along

with the retention of high modulus and thermal stability have been attained. Such improvements in toughness have been attributed to better adhesion and controlled morphology brought about by chemically linking (reacting in) the thermoplastic modifiers to the thermosetting system. The use of such functionalized polymers have also provided the added advantage of better solvent stability in comparison to commercial non-reactive polymers. Furthermore such modified systems have much lower water uptakes in comparison to neat resins.

Cyanate esters form yet another major family of thermosetting resins with applications in electronics, aerospace, adhesives and encapsulants industries. The dicyanate ester monomers cyclotrimerize via addition polymerization to form highly crosslinked polycyanurates as shown in Scheme 1 (6,7). The use of commercial amorphous thermoplastic polysulfones as a means of toughening composite matrices has been reported (8). Such thermoplastic modifiers are essentially of the 'non-reactive' type. This paper addresses the effect of varying back-bone chemistry of the thermoplastic modifier (9,10,11) on the phase behavior, morphologies and mechanical performance of the resulting networks. The solubility parameters (12) of the components (thermoset and thermoplastic) and the kinetics of phase separation largely determine the phase behavior thereby reflecting on the mechanical performance. In the present work we have investigated the use of controlled molecular weight functionalized amorphous bisphenol-A and phenolphthalein based poly(arylene ether)s as potential toughness modifiers. The objective being to design such thermoplastic modifiers which would afford tougher networks without detracting from the high Tg's (~265°C) and good mechanical performance of the unmodified cyanate ester networks.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

Commercial Arocy B-10 [M.P.79°C, d=1.259] [2,2'-Bis(4-cyanatophenyl) propane], provided by Ciba-Geigy, Inc. was the thermosetting system that was evaluated. Aluminium acetylacetonate [Al(acac)] (99%) from Strem Chemicals, Inc. and nonyl phenol (technical grade) from Aldrich constituted the catalyst system that was employed. Bisphenol-A [2,2'-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane] [M.P. 154°C] supplied by Dow Chemicals was recrystallized from toluene. Phenolphthalein (Aldrich Co., analytical grade) was recrystallized from methanol [M.P. 261°C]. 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenylsulfone (DCDPS) supplied by AMOCO was recrystallized from toluene. 4,4'-Difluorobenzophenone (DFBP) supplied by ICI was recrystallized from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether. Dimethyl acetamide (DMAC) obtained from Fisher Scientific was distilled under vacuum. Potassium carbonate and toluene obtained from Fisher Scientific were used as supplied without further purification.

2.2. Poly(Arylene Ether) Oligomers

Hydroxy, cyanato or t-butyl phenyl terminated bisphenol-A or phenolphthalein based amorphous poly(arylene ether)s oligomers of controlled molecular weight were synthesized according to the general procedure provided in reference (13). The oligomers were well characterized for their end-groups and molecular weights by means of intrinsic viscosities, NMR spectroscopy, titrimetry and DSC analyses (9,10,11).

2.3 Resin Processing

The amorphous polymers were dissolved in Arocy B-10 at 90-100°C to obtain a homogeneous melt. The melt was degassed under vacuum to remove any volatiles or entrapped air. As soon as degassing was complete, the catalyst, (250 ppm Al(acac)/2 pph nonyl phenol) was added with stirring and the reaction was further degassed. The hot resin was subsequently poured into pre-heated (100°C) silicone rubber molds for fracture toughness (K_{1C}) tensile dogbone and DMA specimens. The melts were then cured using a cure protocol of 3 h 104°C, 1 h 200°C and 2 h 250°C. The postulated chemical processes leading to the cured network are shown in Scheme 1.

2.4. Test Methods

Differential scanning calorimetry analyses (DSC) were conducted on a DuPont-912 differential scanning calorimeter connected to a DuPont 2100 Thermal Analyst. Dynamic mechanical analyses

(DMA) were performed on a Perkin Elmer DMA-7 dynamic mechanical analyzer connected to a UNIX thermal analysis system. Intrinsic viscosities of the amorphous polymers were obtained in chloroform at 25°C using a Cannon-Ubbelohde viscometer. Number average molecular weights of hydroxy terminated and cyanate ester functionalized polysulfones were estimated via end-group titration. Infrared spectroscopy was carried out on a Nicolet-800 FT-IR spectrophotometer. NMR spectroscopy measurements were done on a Varian Unity-400 MHz spectrometer. Fracture toughness measurements were performed in accordance with ASTM, D-5045-91 (E-399-90) test method on 10-12 specimens of dimensions 3.2mm x 6.5mm x 38mm. Stress-strain measurements were performed in accordance with ASTM, D-638 (Sample-V), using a cross-head speed of 0.05"/min. Morphologies of the fracture surfaces were determined using a scanning electron microscope (International Scientific Instruments Model SX-40) after sputter coating an approximate 100 Å gold film onto the fracture surface using a Bio Rad Polaron (Model E4500). Dynamic and isothermal melt viscosities were measured on a parallel plate Bohlin rheometer system. STEM (Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy) analyses were conducted on Ruthenium oxide stained micro-tomed thin sections. RuO₄ exhibited a preferential staining of the thermoplastic region thus serving as an effective tool in analyses of the morphologies.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extent of reaction after the curing by catalyzed cyclotrimerization of cyanate esters was evaluated by FT-IR to be > 99%. The decrease in peak height due to the C-N stretch was followed with cure with the C-H stretch of the isopropylidene group being used as the reference peak (6). The cured networks had T_g ~265°C.

Various Bisphenol-A based poly(arylene ether sulfone) oligomers (T_g's ~175°C) employed in this study are as shown in Scheme 2. DMA analyses of the 10, 15, 20 and 25 wt.% Bis A-PSF-OCN modified cyanate ester networks suggested the presence of two phases and a considerable extent of phase mixing. The modified networks exhibited negligible improvements in fracture toughness over the unmodified networks. In addition, the fracture surfaces of the both the unmodified and modified networks exhibited no texture and resulted in smooth fracture surfaces. The phase sizes as determined by STEM of RuO₄ stained thin sections [Figure 1] appeared to be ~0.02-0.04 microns. Similar results were also obtained with Bis A-PSF-OH modified networks. Non-reactive Udel modified networks on the other hand exhibited considerable texture in the fracture surface with phase sizes ~0.5 microns. Udel modified networks were tougher than the reactive PSF-OCN and PSF-OH modified networks. Such a behavior was related to the role of solubility parameter (12). One major drawback of the Udel modified networks was in the area of solvent stability. On immersing in chloroform they exhibited extensive solvent stress cracking and disintegrated in minutes (physical blend!). On the other hand the reactive modified networks exhibited superior solvent stability and no stress cracking and this is attributed to the formation of a chemical bond wherein the thermoplastic is reacted into the network.

Based on the above, we attempted to investigate the use of amorphous poly(arylene ether ketone)s [Scheme 3] based on Bisphenol-A as potential toughness modifiers (11). The poly(arylene ether ketone)s (T_g's ~150°C) are known to have a much higher ductility and fracture toughness relative to the corresponding sulfones. In contrast to the Bis A-PSF-OH and Bis A-PSF-OCN modified networks the Bis A-PEK-OH and Bis A-PEK-OCN modified networks exhibited well defined morphologies [Figure 2]. Fracture toughness was seen to increase both with increasing weight percent and increasing back-bone molecular weight of the modifier. [Figure 3] The molecular weight effect was seen to be more pronounced at higher weight percent loadings and this relates to the formation of the phase-inverted morphologies. [Figure 2] For the same back-bone molecular weight, reactive end-groups (-OH and -OCN) afford much better improvements in fracture toughness [Figure 3] in comparison to the non-reactive types (t-Bu) and this is attributed to the better interfacial adhesion in the former case brought about by chemical linkage. The improvements in toughness were attained with a minimal loss in modulus relative to the unmodified networks. We had thus generated tougher networks of comparable moduli but a major drawback was that we had dropped the upper use temperature to <150°C in the process.

This led us to investigate the use of amorphous phenolphthalein based polyarylene ethers [Scheme 4] as potential toughness modifiers. DMA analyses on 10, 20 and 30 wt.% loadings of 15K PPH-PSF-OH modified cyanate ester networks predicted the existence of two phases (two T_g's) as well

as some amount of phase mixing. SEM analyses on the fracture surfaces indicated essentially a multi-phase texture. At 10, wt.% loadings of PPH-PSF-OH the morphology was essentially one where the cyanate ester was the continuous phase with a dispersed thermoplastic phase. At 20 wt.% loadings a lot more connectivity was observed between the thermoplastic domains. 30 wt.% loadings of PPH-PSF-OH resulted in a completely phase inverted morphology. The morphologies were confirmed by staining thin sections of cured samples with Ruthenium oxide and subsequently observing the sections under STEM [Figure 4]. Fracture toughness was seen to increase with increasing incorporations as well as increasing molecular weights of the PPH-PSF-OH modifier [Figure 5]. On the other hand the both DMA and SEM analysis (of the fracture surfaces) of the 15K PPH-PEPO-OH modified networks suggested a lot more phase mixing and resulted in textureless morphologies. This was further reflected in no improvements in fracture toughness [Figure 6]. From these observations one can discern the strong influence of phase separated morphologies on the fracture behavior of the networks. Preliminary investigation of the mechanical properties (stress-strain) of the 15K PPH-PSF-OH modified networks have been conducted and suggest that at 30 wt.% loadings a 4-fold increase in fracture toughness is accompanied with a ~8-10% decrease in modulus [Figure 7]. Furthermore both the unmodified and modified networks have comparable Tg's.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It was possible to synthesize controlled molecular weight amorphous poly(arylene ether)s which were quantitatively functionalized with reactive or non-reactive end-groups. The oligomers were characterized by a variety of techniques. The functionalized oligomers could be co-cured with commercially available Bisphenol-A based cyanate ester resins to obtain thermoplastic modified networks. In the case of the amorphous Bisphenol-A based poly(arylene ether ketone) modified networks a >4-fold increase in toughness was achieved at a minimal loss in modulus, at the cost of an undesirable reduction in the upper use temperature (<150°C). The phenolphthalein based poly(arylene ether sulfone)s on the other hand afforded similar improvements without significantly affecting the upper use temperature (Tg ~265°C). Studies to investigate potential applications of these modified networks in the areas of high temperature composite matrices and adhesives are in progress.

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Scheme 1. Cyclotrimerization of cyanate esters.

Scheme 2. Bisphenol-A based amorphous poly(arylene ether sulfone)s employed in this study.

HYDROXY FUNCTIONALIZED POLY(ARYLENE ETHER KETONE)

HYDROXY FUNCTIONALIZED POLY(ARYLENE ETHER SULFONE)

HYDROXY FUNCTIONALIZED POLY(ARYLENE ETHER PHOSPHINE OXIDE)

Scheme 4. Phenolphthalein based amorphous poly(arylene ether)s employed in this study.

10% 15K Bis A-PSF-OCN

25% 15K Bis A-PSF-OCN

Figure 1. STEM of RuO₄ stained thin sections. [Bar = 0.5 μ]

10% 15K Bis A-PEK-OH

25% 15K Bis A-PEK-OH

Figure 2. STEM of RuO₄ stained thin sections. [Bar = 0.5 μ]

Figure 3. Fracture toughness (K_{1c}) as a function of bisphenol-A based poly(arylene ether ketone) concentration.

10% 15K PPH-PSF-OH

20% 15K PPH-PSF-OH

30% 15K PPH-PSF-OH

Figure 4. STEM of RuO₄ stained thin sections. [Bar = 0.5 μ]

Figure 5. Fracture toughness as a function of modifier concentration.

Figure 6. Fracture toughness as a function of modifier concentration.

Figure 7. Moduli and strength of 15K phenolphthalein based poly(arylene ether sulfone) concentration.

INTERMETALLICS

